

**IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO CHILDREN AT AN EARLY AGE:
PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS**

Dushatova Shoxsanam Baxtiyor qizi

Fergana State University, teacher, sh.dushatova@pf.fdu.uz

Qurbonaliyeva Munira Usmonali qizi

Fergana State University, 3rd year student

Abstract: Nowadays, the process of globalization requires people to learn several foreign languages in addition to their mother tongue. Current research shows that starting this process at an early age is more effective. Our country, Uzbekistan, also pays close attention to this issue, and programs have been developed and are being released based on a new approach to teaching foreign languages, especially English, in cooperation with the world's leading organizations and universities.

Key words: foreign language, language learning at an early age, educational games, role-playing games, manual labor.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, this process has been developing especially in pre-school educational institutions. Many large-scale projects are being implemented to teach English in state-owned and private pre-school educational institutions. This article highlights the importance of using educational games in teaching foreign languages, especially English, from an early age, as well as the easy acquisition of language skills through various games.

Due to the fact that the main and favorite activity of children of kindergarten and school age is the game, they begin to discover the world through the game. If foreign languages are taught by mixing them into the game, this will increase the efficiency of mastering language skills several times. The game helps to form a child's mental alertness and increase his physical activity, and strengthens the child's

self-confidence, as well as helps in the formation of social relations with others. For this reason, it is necessary for parents and educators to encourage the child to learn with as many different games as possible. It is through games that a child discovers his talent along with learning. To achieve this, it is considered appropriate to use an environment that activates sensory organs, especially auditory and kinesthetic types of active education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Educational games are playing musical instruments, mainly singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, in which cartoons that are understandable to them are more useful, hand includes making various things through labor. In response to the question of how old it is best to learn foreign languages, scientists from around the world have unanimously agreed that a child under the age of 10 can learn a foreign language easily. During this period, the child learns languages not by understanding, but mechanically, so the use and pronunciation of a foreign language is easily mastered. However, considering that the child is born with the ability to imitate the sounds of any language, there are many people who think about starting this process earlier. The results of the research on the study of the human brain have shown that the period from the birth of the baby to the age of three is the most important period of the child's development. [3,14] It has also been found that the brain of a three-year-old child works twice as fast as the brain of an adult. Therefore, according to English experts, introducing a second language to a child in the first year will help him learn it easily. But in any case, we must not forget that taking into account the child's language acquisition and psychological abilities is an extremely important factor.

Every child is a unique individual, naturally, their developmental stages are also different from each other. According to psychologists, forcing a child to speak from an early age or trying to develop him like his peers in many cases has the opposite effect and leads to bad results. When teaching a foreign language to children of kindergarten and junior school age, it is necessary to take into account

psychological and pedagogical features, that is, their curiosity and enthusiasm. We should also remember that children cannot focus on one type of activity for a long time. Parents want their children to be mature in all aspects, and in many cases, they try to give him assignments in various subjects, teach him a language, or involve him in sports without taking into account his psychological and physiological readiness. In most cases, when parents fail to achieve the expected results, they try to influence the child by reprimanding the child or comparing him to his peers. But these attempts also weaken the child's interest in learning and cause his interest in the surrounding things to fade. The role of parents and educators in preventing such unfortunate situations is incomparable. The easiest and most appropriate way to teach a child to think freely, to strengthen his curiosity and interest in learning the environment, to enrich a child's imagination, and to bring out his creativity is this game. When children play, they put their ideas into practice, test their hypotheses, acquire necessary skills, use their imaginations, and discover their own worlds.

The importance of the game

Children are naturally very curious and use all their senses to explore the world around them. Since the game is one of the most basic and favorite activities of the child, if the child is introduced to the world and all the necessary knowledge and skills in it through the game, the efficiency of learning will increase several times. The game not only increases the physical activity of the child, but it also helps to form mental freshness. The game helps to strengthen the child's self-confidence and to form social relations with the surrounding people. Therefore, parents and educators should encourage children to learn through play as much as possible. It is through games that children learn and discover their talents. To achieve this, the use of an environment that activates sensory organs, including auditory and kinesthetic types of active education, plays an important role. Educational games include playing musical instruments and dancing, singing songs, reciting poems, playing games on various topics, watching videos, playing the role of cartoon characters, singing their songs, etc. It includes making various things with the help of labor.

Colorful exhibitions, learning maps through geographic games, competitions on various topics, role-playing games, making different shapes with plasticine are one of the most interesting ways to develop children's physical and mental activities. [8.3] Children play, develop and learn. Playing with plasticine, children develop the skill of "fine mechanics". When children make shapes in plasticine, eye and hand activities are coordinated and hand and finger muscles are strengthened. This, in turn, is one of the most necessary skills before the formation of writing skills, because strong muscle strength and "eye-hand coordination" help children to hold and use writing instruments correctly. will help a lot. Also, by playing with plasticine, children learn about the color, shape and structure of objects. In the games of educational activities with the participation of musical instruments, children begin to distinguish different tones. Children begin to understand the sounds coming from different instruments and how the pitch changes. The speed and quietness of the music moves according to the pitch and pitch of the sound curtains. When playing with transport toys, children test the power of friction and movement by going up and down, forward and backward, fast and slow. they learn the concepts of size, height, length, vertical and horizontal.

Educational games that encourage children to communicate. Young children learn through their feelings and actions, so learning English should also be done through these feelings. Engaging young children in interesting and communicative situations and activities in learning English is a very important factor for acquiring language skills. Although the purpose of the activity is to teach English, it can attract children like a game, and children will be involved in these activities without thinking, and children will learn the foreign language as naturally as their mother tongue. it is also necessary to pay special attention. Creating interesting and motivating situations for young children to learn English and ensuring that children actively participate in it is one of the most important situations, especially nowadays. Situations Educational activities. Since the basis of any situation and activities is the teaching of the English language, it is desirable that these activities be conducted in

English in a fluent and comprehensible manner. It is necessary to reduce the communication in the mother tongue and give the main emphasis to the English language. Of course, the teacher's ability to attract a child with his actions, gestures, fluent speech and speaking tone in English is one of the first and main successes in language teaching. In particular, the use of educational activities by language teachers, such as "Playing with blocks or legos", "Dressing", "Animals and their sounds", "Crafts", Sing a song, Thematic visual aids [8.1], helps young children to learn language. is one of the convenient ways to form learning skills. Using these activities, we will have the opportunity to expand and develop children's vocabulary, imagination and creative thinking. "Playing with blocks or legos". It has been proven in practice that when it is aimed to give children an understanding of shapes, colors and numbers in English, it is better to learn them through the use of blocks, cubes and legos. Playing with blocks, cubes and lego toys encourages the child to think and bring out his creative ability in doing something, and at the same time, through these games, the child's vocabulary in English begins to appear. Vocabulary through games is carried out by asking questions in English and conveying the main concepts through instructions. The child learns to count and sort through this game: How many blocks are there? Shall we put the red ones here? They learn the location of things through prepositions: in, on, under, below, behind, next to. They also understand the units of measurement: big, small, long, short. With the help of the following words, instructions are given to what the child is making: Find the yellow block, please! Pull the pink one, please!, push them!, Build the house, please! make the car, please! The objects and shapes that the child is making are described: square, rectangle, tower, house, castle, garden. Through the "Dressing" educational activity, it is also possible to introduce children to fairy-tale heroes of the peoples of the world.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When introducing characters of fairy tales to children, dressing them in their clothes and acting out roles in English with short dialogues and easy-to-understand

words increases the child's English vocabulary and expands the child's imagination and worldview. Of course, through this educational activity, children will learn words related to human body parts and clothes and will have the opportunity to use them in practice. Human body parts: head, arm, hands, foot (feet), legs, eyes, ear, nose... Clothes: dress, shirt, t-shirt, shoes, slippers, cap, belt, gloves... is given with an emphasis on the words: put your arms through here, tie this around your waist/wrist, put these on your feet — first your right foot, then your left foot, put this over your head. Also, children bring to life the heroes of fairy tales in their imagination, get into the image and begin to learn to use basic words and phrases.

This will definitely help the child to listen and understand words in English and to develop speaking skills by creating sentences from memorized words. Fairy, princess, pirate, king, queen, clown clothes are described, and phrases related to wearing clothes are used: put on, zip up, do the buttons up, unbutton, unzip. In the educational activity "Animals and their sounds" the world of animals and insects will be introduced in English. Children also listen to various fairy tales with the participation of animals. Learning about animals, insects and their movements and sounds in English through colorful pictures of animals is also a fun activity for children. Domestic animals: dog, cat, duck, cock, hen, chicken, cow, mouse, horse, pig, donkey... Wild animals: lion, tiger, wolf, rabbit, fox, snake, deer, bear, monkey... Learning the names of animals and insects in children's English and imitating their actions gives the child a lot of pleasure. "Crafts" Handiwork: making and decorating things is an educational activity. Everyone knows that a child is curious by nature, but it should be remembered that the development process of a child does not happen in the same way at one time. Some children may have different stages of development due to their social background, nature and interests. Some children are quiet and cannot quickly join the crowd, but because they are observant, their creativity is well developed. If such children are involved in the activity of making things by means of manual labor, they will undoubtedly grow up to be real inventors of works of art. When children are taught to make colorful things through

manual labor, the child's creative abilities develop, and when this activity is conducted in English, English vocabulary increases, and listening comprehension and speaking skills are also developed. So, this type of educational activity can be making shapes from pieces of paper, coloring shapes with paints, or making different things from plasticine. Any process should not be without English words and phrases. The name of each tool and material should be conveyed to children in English: paint, crayon, marker, card, paper, shiny paper, newspaper, glue, scissors, cotton wool, fabric, feathers. Instructions must be in English: paint, draw, color, smudge blow, copy, pour, make, cut, stick, decorate, hang it up. Sing a song. One of the most enjoyable activities for children. Children are inclined to sing from a young age, and through singing, children not only increase their vocabulary, but also learn to say words in tune. One of the most popular types of English songs sung by young children is the song "Rain, Rain go away". Rain, rain, go away Come again another day Daddy wants to play Rain, rain go away... If the educational game is carried out with the help of umbrellas, artificial clouds and artificial fire, the activity of children will increase, the result will increase the effectiveness of children in the game analyze participation. It is necessary to ensure active participation of children in educational activities, pay attention to each child separately and encourage the child to learn something in this activity. Praising successful children for their work also increases their motivation. But according to psychologists, it is said that praise should be focused not on the person, but on the work done. Because if the praise is given to a person, it can lead the child to arrogance later. Praise for work ensures that any work will be done quickly and qualitatively. [10,14]

CONCLUSION

To sum up, how children study in school and grow up with high goals depends to a large extent on the family environment, the attention of the neighborhood, and education in the preschool educational institution. The scientific observations and research given in the article show that 70% of all the information a person receives during his life before the age of 6 shows the importance of preschool education in

the development of a child's personality. This is of course very important. At a meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev on August 16, 2017, in order to determine measures for 100% coverage of 5-6-year-old children in preschool educational institutions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On organizing the activities of the Ministry" was adopted. We all know that the goal of the state requirements is to educate a mentally perfect and intellectually developed person in the preschool education system, taking into account the socio-economic reforms carried out in the country, the advanced experience of foreign countries and the achievements of science and modern information and communication technologies. we know So, it is not for nothing that the knowledge acquired by children in their early years is "set in stone" as our ancestors said. Based on this point of view, teaching foreign languages to children at an early age is the reason for easy acquisition of language skills and abilities. Especially if these knowledge, skills and abilities are taught through various games and educational activities, the child learns foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue. Educational games not only form knowledge, skills and abilities in a child, but at the same time, they also ensure the child's healthy physical development, refresh mentally, strengthen self-confidence, and are a great help in forming social relations with others. will give.

References:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 9 sentyabrdagi «Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini tubdan takomillatirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida»gi PQ-3261-son qarori; O‘z DSt 17368–2020 “Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiyaning davlat standartini tasdiqlash haqida”.
2. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarbiyalanuvchilari va boshlang‘ich maktab o‘quvchilariga chet tilini o‘rgatishda o‘yinlar. Baxramova M. D. Tuzuvchi: Baxramova M. D., — T.2016
3. Dushatova, S. (2022). EVFEMIZM TUSHUNCHASI TAHLILI.

4. Dushatova, S. (2022). LINGUISTIC AND SOCIAL ORIGINATION OF TABOOS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 318-321.
5. Dushatova, S., & Tursunaliyev, M. (2022). CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING INSON RIVOJLANISHIGA TASIRI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(7), 133-138.
6. Dushatova, S., & Azamov, M. (2022, November). SO'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 89-95).
7. Dushatova, S., & qizi Norinboyeva, D. J. (2022). CHET TILIDA NUTQNI TINGLAB TUSHUNISH VA UNDA FRAZEOLOGIZMLARNING O'RNII. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 1(7), 66-71.
8. Dushatova, S., & Burgutova, G. (2022). CHET TILLARINI BILISHNING FOYDALARI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 40-45.
9. кизи Гиёсова, В. А. (2022). ТОТЕМИСТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕ СКАЗОК О ЖИВОТНЫХ. *THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD*, 1(1), 133-139.
10. Bahodirovna, K. M. (2022). "ALIEN" ALBERT CAMUS AND THE PHENOMENON OF GETTING STRANGER. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 709-714.
11. Bakhodirovich, A. B. (2022). "Alchemist" Paolo Coelho. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 2(4), 105-108.
12. Xaitov, L. A. (2021, December). THE ISSUE OF SUSTENANCE AND PROFESSION IN HAKIM TERMIZI'S WORK "BAYANUL KASB"("DESCRIPTION OF THE PROFESSION"). In *International Scientific and Current Research Conferences* (pp. 67-69).

13. Dushatova, S., & Mamajonova, S. (2022). ICEBERG PRINCIPLE" AS A STYLISTIC FEATURE OF E. HEMINGWAY'S SHORT STORY "THE OLD MAN AND THE SEA. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 1931-1934.
14. Faxriddin o'g'li, Y. H. (2022). An Analysis of How Language Forms Cross-Cultural Ties. *Academia Open*, 7, 10-21070.
15. Shokhsanam, D., & Abdukarimova, M. (2022, December). THE ADVANTAGES OF BOOKS IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY* (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 169-171).
16. Shokhsanam, D., & Makhmudova, M. (2022). BENEFITS OF DAILY READING. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 1(8), 28-32.
17. Ismoilova, M., Maqsudova, G., Sharipova, S., & Yuldasheva, D. (2022). COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY: TYPES, SUBJECT MATTER, TASKS, APPROACHES AND CLASSIFICATION. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 1544-1546.
18. Boxodirova, F., Isroilova, D., Abduraxmanov, M., & Yuldasheva, D. (2022). DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING THE GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF CONJUNCTIONS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 1421-1422.
19. Tursunovich, S. E. (2023). Actual Issues of Teaching Pragmatic Competences to English Language Learners in Uzbekistan. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 148-152.
20. Tursunovich, S. E. (2021). THE ROLE OF PRAGMATICS IN OVERCOMING CHALLENGES OF ACADEMIC WRITING. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 247-249.